

**IMPLEMENTATION OF NATIONAL INDIGENOUS PEOPLE (IP) EDUCATION
POLICY FRAMEWORK AND THE LEVEL OF PRACTICE OF INDIGENOUS
KNOWLEDGE SYSTEM PRACTICES (IKPS) IN THE CALABARZON REGION:
BASIS FOR INNOVATIVE IPED CURRICULUM MODEL**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10575689>

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) Policy Framework and Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices in CALABARZON. Using a quantitative approach, teachers from five Department of Education divisions were surveyed. Statistical methods, including frequency distribution and Kruskal Wallis H-Test, were applied to analyze data, revealing significant differences in IPEd Policy Framework implementation and its impact on curriculum, competencies, content, learning space, and environment. Longer implementation periods improved Indigenous Peoples' learning experiences. Learning resources and assessment were affected by the duration of IP education. Teaching methodologies, strategies, and training showed uniformity across school profiles. The study found no significant differences in Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices based on school profiles but noted a positive influence from teacher training, indicating higher training correlating with greater preservation and promotion. A significant relationship between IPEd Policy Framework implementation and Indigenous Knowledge practice was established, emphasizing the pivotal role of teacher training and program duration. The study underscored the importance of a holistic approach to indigenous education, considering policy implementation and cultural preservation in tandem.

Keywords: *Indigenous Education; Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices (IKSPs)*

INTRODUCTION

This dissertation critically examined the historical trajectory of the Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) Policy Framework and its consequential impact on indigenous education (DepEd Memorandum No. 62, s. 2011; DepEd Memorandum No. 32, s. 2015). These policies, molded by the specter of historical injustices, sought to redress the enduring educational disparities experienced by indigenous populations, placing paramount importance on the preservation of cultural heritage, language revitalization, and academic achievement (United Nations, 2017). Rooted in a robust theoretical framework centered on culturally relevant education, the study acknowledged that aligning educational practices with the cultural context of indigenous learners enhances overall effectiveness.

In the Philippine context, the Department of Education historically endorsed a national indigenous education policy through DepEd Memorandum No. 62, s. 2011, and DepEd Memorandum No. 32, s. 2015, articulating the unequivocal right of indigenous peoples to a basic education that is culturally rooted and responsive. Despite the legal safeguards provided by the Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act, enacted into law in 1997 (The World Bank, 2022), which guarantees access to fundamental healthcare and education for indigenous populations, persistent prejudices and educational gaps continue to afflict the indigenous community, comprising 10-20% of the nation's population (Eduardo and Gabriel, 2021).

Against this historical backdrop, the study explored the intricate connection between the IPEd Policy Framework and the historical practice of Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP), accentuating the imperative of cultural competence and respect. To enhance the historical implementation, the dissertation proposed a structured IPEd Curriculum Model, envisioning a comprehensive plan that outlines specific historical objectives, guidelines, and strategies for seamlessly infusing IKSPs into the curriculum. The proposed historical plan encompassed comprehensive teacher training programs, collaborative platforms for educators to share historical best practices, and the development of historically informed and culturally relevant teaching materials (Mercado, 2020). This structured historical approach aimed to ensure that the integration of IKSPs in the educational framework was not only cohesive and consistent but also historically meaningful, contributing significantly to a more effective and equitable incorporation of indigenous knowledge within the formal education system in CALABARZON.

Research Questions

This study aimed to find out the extent of implementation of the Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) Policy Framework and the level of practice of the Indigenous Knowledge

System and Practices in the CALABARZON region as basis for Innovative IPed curriculum model.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the school profile of the IP schools in the CALABARZON Region in terms of:
 - 1.1 No. of years of implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework;
 - 1.2 No. of IP students enrolled;
 - 1.3 No. of teachers trained for Indigenous People Education; and
 - 1.4 No. of teachers trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices?
2. What is the level of implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework among elementary schools in terms of:
 - 2.1 Curriculum Design, Competencies and Content;
 - 2.2 Teaching Methodologies and Strategies;
 - 2.3 Learning Space and Environment;
 - 2.4 Learning Resources;
 - 2.5 Teacher Training; and
 - 2.6 Classroom Assessment?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework when grouped into school profile?
 - 3.1 No. of years of implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework;
 - 3.2 No. of IP students enrolled;
 - 3.3 No. of teachers trained for Indigenous People Education; and
 - 3.4 No. of teachers trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices?
4. What is the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices among of the IPed schools in CALABARZON Region?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices of the IPed schools when grouped into school profile?
 - 5.1 No. of years of implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework;
 - 5.2 No. of IP students enrolled;
 - 5.3 No. of teachers trained for Indigenous People Education; and
 - 5.4 No. of teachers trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework and level of practice of the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices?
7. What are the challenges encountered by the school in terms of the following:
 - 7.1 Implementation of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework; and
 - 7.2 Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices?
8. What are the strategies applied by the school to address the challenges encountered in terms of:
 - 8.1 Implementation of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework; and
 - 8.2 Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices?
9. What curriculum model for Indigenous People Education could be developed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

As it focuses on the experiences of indigenous people in the Philippines, particularly from the CALABAZON region, the study adhered to the quantitative research approach. This design is fitted to the study at hand as it shall reveal the state of implementation of the Indigenous People Education (IPEd) here in the Philippines. It was conducted using the Linear Sequential Model (Royce, 1970), a framework for systems design applied to social research comprising three main stages: fact-finding and discovery; retrieval and tabulation of data; and analysis, interpretation, and presentation of data. The research population consisted of teachers and school heads from the Batangas, Rizal, and Quezon divisions of the Department of Education in CALABARZON. These divisions were selected because they are known to implement the Indigenous Education Program (IPEd). The respondents were specifically teachers handling Indigenous Peoples (IP) learners and schools actively involved in the implementation of the IP Education Program. The researcher-developed survey underwent expert validation and reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient to ensure internal consistency. After a review for substance and dependability, the validated instrument was distributed to the intended respondents. Four experts were involved in the validation, and the sample size for reliability testing was determined by a statistician. The research instrument comprises five parts: Part I gathers school data from the head, while Parts II–V are for teachers handling Indigenous Peoples (IP) learners. Data collection utilized Google Forms, a choice made by respondents for its ease of use. Adhering to ethical research practices, a request letter signed by the researcher and acknowledged by the dissertation adviser accompanied the research instrument. Following the administration of questionnaires via Google Forms, the researcher collected and downloaded the responses, subsequently conducting a thorough analysis and interpretation of the gathered data. The collected data underwent meticulous organization to facilitate streamlined analysis and interpretation. Various statistical tools were applied to address specific Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs): percentage calculations for SOPs 1, 7, and 8; computations of the weighted mean for SOPs 2 and 4. For SOPs 3 and 5, the Kruskal Wallis H-Test was employed to examine significant differences, while the Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used for SOP No. 6 to assess any significant relationships. Likert scales were thoughtfully implemented to ensure an objective and accurate measure of each respondent's answers. Consistently, a scale of 1 to 5 was utilized across all Likert scales, promoting uniformity and facilitating easy comparison and contrast of values when necessary.

RESULTS

1. School Profile

1.1 No. of Years of Implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework

No. of Years in Implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 to 3 years	1	5
4 to 6 years	0	0
7 to 9 years	11	58
10 years and above	7	37
Total	19	100.00

1.2 Frequency Distribution of the School in terms of f IP Students Enrolled

No. of IP Students Enrolled	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-25	10	52
26-50	5	26
51-75	2	11
76 and above	2	11
Total	19	100.00

1.3 Frequency Distribution in terms of No. of School Trained/Not Trained for Indigenous People Education

No. of Schools Trained for Indigenous People Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Not Trained on Indigenous Education Policy Framework	9	47
Trained in the District Level	3	16
Trained in the Division Level	5	26
Trained in the Regional Level	2	11
Trained in the National Level	0	0
Total	19	100.00

1.4 Frequency Distribution of the in terms of No. of Schools Trained/Not Trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices

No. of Schools Trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Not Trained on Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices (IKSPs)	5	26
Trained in the District Level	2	11
Trained in the Division Level	9	47

Trained in the Regional Level	3	16
Trained in the National Level	0	0
Total	19	100.00

2. Level of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework among Schools

2.1 Mean Scores of the Level of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework among Elementary Schools in terms of Curriculum Design, Competencies, and Content

Curriculum Design, Competencies and Content	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Anchors the learning context on the ancestral domain, the community's worldview, and its indigenous cultural institution.	4.34	Mostly Implemented
2. Includes and respects the community's expression of spirituality as part of the curriculum's context.	4.76	Fully Implemented
3. Affirms and strengthens indigenous cultural identity.	4.70	Fully Implemented
4. Revitalizes, regenerates, strengthens, and enriches IKSPs, ILS and indigenous languages.	4.37	Mostly Implemented
5. Emphasizes competencies that are needed to support the development and protection of the ancestral domain, the vitality of their culture, and the advancement of indigenous people's rights and welfare.	4.69	Fully Implemented
6. Discuss with the community about new concepts and competencies that is linked to the life experience of the community.	4.62	Fully Implemented
Grand Mean:	4.58	Fully Implemented

Legend: "Not Implemented (1.00 – 1.50)", "Partially Implemented (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Implemented (2.51 – 3.50)", "Mostly Implemented 3.51 – 4.50)", "Fully Implemented (4.51 – 5.00)"

2.2 Mean Scores of the Level of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework among Elementary Schools in terms of Teaching Methodologies and Strategies

Teaching Methodologies and Strategies	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The spiritual dimensions of teaching and learning is recognized and included in planning learning activities.	4.62	Fully Implemented
2. Rituals related to particular IKSPs to be learned are purview and planned with community elders.	4.12	Mostly Implemented

3. Recognize that the main transmitter of IKSPs are the culture bearers and they bare also active knowledge managers in teaching-learning process.	4.51	Fully Implemented
4. Ensure that the IKSPs holders and culture bearers does not only provide and validate information but also facilitate learning.	4.45	Mostly Implemented
5. Teaching methodologies and strategies are given premium and ensure that the learning styles and processes on “IP learners are cultivated and nurtured	4.46	Mostly Implemented
6. Make sure that introduction and application of teaching methodologies and strategies from outside are discussed first with the community.	4.40	Mostly Implemented
Grand Mean:	4.43	Mostly Implemented

Legend: “Not Implemented (1.00 – 1.50)”, “Partially Implemented (1.51 – 2.50)”, “Moderately Implemented (2.51 – 3.50)”, “Mostly Implemented 3.51 – 4.50)”, “Fully Implemented (4.51 – 5.00)”

2.3 Mean Scores of the Level of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework among Elementary Schools in terms of Learning Space and Environment

Learning Space and Environment	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The classroom setting is culturally appropriate.	4.45	Mostly Implemented
2. The teacher ensure that the ancestral domain where IKSPs are experienced, lived and learned is the primary learning environment.	4.48	Mostly Implemented
3. The teaching and learning process are designed to maximize the ancestral domain and the activities of the community.	4.29	Mostly Implemented
4. Provide a combination of classroom-based session that foster the appreciation of lifelong learning but also deepen the relationship with the ancestral domain.	4.40	Mostly Implemented
5. Sought the guidance of the community when designing activities that involve in going to particular places in the ancestral domain to ensure that sacred places will be violated.	4.26	Mostly Implemented
6. Observed and respects cultural norms while going and staying in the learning area.	4.78	Fully Implemented
Grand Mean:	4.44	Mostly Implemented

Legend: “Not Implemented (1.00 – 1.50)”, “Partially Implemented (1.51 – 2.50)”, “Moderately Implemented (2.51 – 3.50)”, “Mostly Implemented 3.51 – 4.50)”, “Fully Implemented (4.51 – 5.00)”

2.4 Mean Scores of the Level of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework among Elementary Schools in terms of Learning Resources

Learning Resources	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Learning materials and other learning resources being used are culturally generated.	4.26	Mostly Implemented
2. The teacher makes use of the ancestral domain itself as a source of variety of learning resources.	4.12	Mostly Implemented
3. The language use in instructional materials especially in the primary years highlights the use of mother tongue which is determined by the community.	3.98	Mostly Implemented
4. The teacher observes the cultural sensitivities and protocols (consent seeking, validation) in the development and use of learning resources.	4.39	Mostly Implemented
5. Makes sure that protocols in the development of learning resources are published and discussed and agreed upon with the community to protect intellectual property rights.	4.26	Mostly Implemented
Grand Mean:	4.20	Mostly Implemented

Legend: "Not Implemented (1.00 – 1.50)", "Partially Implemented (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Implemented (2.51 – 3.50)", "Mostly Implemented (3.51 – 4.50)", "Fully Implemented (4.51 – 5.00)"

2.5 Mean Scores of the Level of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework among Elementary Schools in terms of Teacher Training

Teacher Training	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The teacher is familiar with indigenous culture as well as the national culture.	3.49	Moderately Implemented
2. The teacher is familiar with indigenous languages as well as the national language.	3.21	Moderately Implemented
3. The teacher is respectful to indigenous concepts and values regarding education.	3.69	Mostly Implemented
4. The teacher is respectful to indigenous concepts and values who engage in an interactive process with indigenous communities and students.	3.71	Mostly Implemented
5. The teacher is using and creating responsive and experiential teaching methods in cooperation and consultation with the indigenous community	3.53	Mostly Implemented
6. The teacher is trained in bilingual teaching methods.	2.94	Moderately Implemented
7. The teacher is trained in language-training methodology	2.98	Moderately Implemented

8. The teacher is open to continuous assessment of their work	3.52	Mostly Implemented
9. The teacher is trained in teacher-training programs organized in cooperation with indigenous people organization and communities	3.21	Moderately Implemented
10. The teacher is trained in teacher-training facilities organized in cooperation with indigenous people's organization and communities	3.37	Moderately Implemented
11. The teacher is selected in consultation with indigenous communities.	3.17	Moderately Implemented
12. The teacher is familiar and trained with IP language (Mother-Tongue)	3.03	Moderately Implemented
Grand Mean:	3.32	Moderately Implemented

Legend: "Not Implemented (1.00 – 1.50)", "Partially Implemented (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Implemented (2.51 – 3.50)", "Mostly Implemented 3.51 – 4.50)", "Fully Implemented (4.51 – 5.00)"

2.6 Mean Scores of the Level of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework among Elementary Schools in terms of Classroom Assessment

Classroom Assessment	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Assessment of the learning done utilizing tools which are culturally appropriate and designed to address the needs and concerns of the community	4.38	Mostly Implemented
2. Community-generated assessment processes is included in the range of assessment methods and tools.	4.31	Mostly Implemented
3. The teacher consider the community values and culture when using assessment generated outside the community.	4.45	Mostly Implemented
4. The teacher make use of paper and pencil test when assessing learning outcomes.	4.57	Fully Implemented
5. The teachers modifies assessment without sacrificing the objective and essence of the assessment process	4.39	Mostly Implemented
6. Ensure that assessment processes foster lifelong learning competencies that includes preparation for community responsibility.	4.48	Mostly Implemented
7. The teacher uses assessment tools and exercises that consist oh higher order thinking skills and integrative understanding across subject areas.	4.39	Mostly Implemented
Grand Mean:	4.42	Mostly Implemented

Legend: "Not Implemented (1.00 – 1.50)", "Partially Implemented (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Implemented (2.51 – 3.50)", "Mostly Implemented 3.51 – 4.50)", "Fully Implemented (4.51 – 5.00)"

3. Test for Significant Difference in the Degree of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework when Grouped into School Profile

3.1 Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Degree of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework when the Respondents are Grouped According to No. of Years of Implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework

Indicators	No. of Years of Implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Curriculum Design, Competencies, and Content	1 to 3 years	0.00	18.510	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	4 to 6 years	0.00				
	7 to 9 years	70.75				
	10 years and above	42.67				
Teaching Methodologies and Strategies	1 to 3 years	0.00	3.706	0.054	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	4 to 6 years	0.00				
	7 to 9 years	65.41				
	10 years and above	52.71				
Learning Space and Environment	1 to 3 years	0.00	3.892	0.049	Reject Ho	Significant
	4 to 6 years	0.00				
	7 to 9 years	56.48				
	10 years and above	69.50				
Learning Resources	1 to 3 years	0.00	4.742	0.029	Reject Ho	Significant
	4 to 6 years	0.00				
	7 to 9 years	56.04				
	10 years and above	70.33				
Teacher Training	1 to 3 years	0.00	3.216	0.073	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	4 to 6 years	0.00				
	7 to 9 years	56.87				
	10 years and above	68.76				
Classroom Assessment	1 to 3 years	0.00	12.189	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	4 to 6 years	0.00				
	7 to 9 years	52.97				
	10 years and above	76.10				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

3.2 Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Degree of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework when the Respondents are Grouped According to IP Students Enrolled

Indicators	No. of IP Students Enrolled	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Curriculum Design, Competencies, and Content	1-25	49.93	5.688	0.128	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	26-50	67.90				
	51-75	59.53				
	76 and above	66.52				
Teaching Methodologies and Strategies	1-25	64.91	3.898	0.273	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	26-50	71.33				
	51-75	56.68				
	76 and above	55.30				
Learning Space and Environment	1-25	61.65	9.648	0.022	Reject Ho	Significant
	26-50	69.67				
	51-75	76.58				
	76 and above	50.36				
Learning Resources	1-25	57.49	5.775	0.123	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	26-50	59.36				
	51-75	78.32				
	76 and above	57.28				
Teacher Training	1-25	58.51	5.725	0.126	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	26-50	66.24				
	51-75	75.74				
	76 and above	54.50				
Classroom Assessment	1-25	65.91	20.642	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	26-50	57.26				
	51-75	89.39				
	76 and above	47.64				

3.3 Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Degree of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework when the Respondents are Grouped According to No. of Schools Trained for Indigenous People Education

Indicators	No. of Teachers Trained for Indigenous People Education	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
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Curriculum Design, Competencies, and Content	Not Trained on Indigenous Education Policy Framework	51.39	17.940	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	26.36				
	Trained in the Division Level	66.20				
	Trained in the Regional Level	77.73				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				
Teaching Methodologies and Strategies	Not Trained on Indigenous Education Policy Framework	59.28	8.312	0.040	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	33.77				
	Trained in the Division Level	65.75				
	Trained in the Regional Level	60.04				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				
Learning Space and Environment	Not Trained on Indigenous Education Policy Framework	68.28	3.427	0.330	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Trained in the District Level	47.64				
	Trained in the Division Level	62.11				
	Trained in the Regional Level	53.08				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				
Learning Resources	Not Trained on Indigenous Education Policy Framework	84.52	30.363	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	29.68				
	Trained in the Division Level	63.65				

	Trained in the Regional Level	30.81				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				
Teacher Training	Not Trained on Indigenous Education Policy Framework	49.43	31.944	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	46.82				
	Trained in the Division Level	57.92				
	Trained in the Regional Level	111.00				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				
Classroom Assessment	Not Trained on Indigenous Education Policy Framework	66.35	13.804	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	26.23				
	Trained in the Division Level	62.04				
	Trained in the Regional Level	75.04				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				

3.4 Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Degree of Implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework when the Respondents are Grouped According to No. of Schools Trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices

Indicators	No. of Teachers Trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Curriculum Design, Competencies, and Content	Not Trained on Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	49.13	21.091	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

	Trained in the District Level	28.75				
	Trained in the Division Level	71.09				
	Trained in the Regional Level	70.55				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				
Teaching Methodologies and Strategies	Not Trained on Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	60.14	9.601	0.022	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	32.75				
	Trained in the Division Level	66.40				
	Trained in the Regional Level	63.82				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				
Learning Space and Environment	Not Trained on Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	69.16	10.805	0.013	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	52.42				
	Trained in the Division Level	65.33				
	Trained in the Regional Level	39.47				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				
Learning Resources	Not Trained on Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	82.70	35.384	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	29.08				
	Trained in the Division Level	64.47				
	Trained in the Regional Level	34.03				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				

Teacher Training	Not Trained on Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	54.22	7.266	0.064	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Trained in the District Level	52.17				
	Trained in the Division Level	60.59				
	Trained in the Regional Level	79.26				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				
Classroom Assessment	Not Trained on Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	76.23	16.393	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	29.83				
	Trained in the Division Level	58.12				
	Trained in the Regional Level	63.82				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				

4. Level of Practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices of the IPEd Schools in CALABARZON.

Mean Scores of the Level of Practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices of the IPEd Schools in CALABARZON Region

Level of Practice	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The teacher respect and recognize the ownership of indigenous communities as the holder of their indigenous knowledge	4.81	Highly Practiced
2. The teacher respect and recognize the ownership of indigenous communities as holders for their specific ways of generating and transmitting knowledge with the participation and informed consent if indigenous communities and elders in the planning of programs.	4.77	Highly Practiced
3. The teacher identifies and incorporate relevant local cultural knowledge with participation and consent of the indigenous communities and elders in the planning of programs.	4.61	Highly Practiced
4. The teacher identifies and incorporate relevant local cultural knowledge with participation and consent of the indigenous communities and elders in selecting teaching methods	4.56	Highly Practiced

5. The teacher identifies and incorporate relevant local cultural knowledge with participation and consent of the indigenous communities and elders in the design of the curricula	4.57	Highly Practiced
6. The teacher identifies and incorporate relevant local cultural knowledge with participation and consent of the indigenous communities and elders in the production of educational materials.	4.54	Highly Practiced
7. The teacher produced indigenized stories, diaries, textbooks etc.	4.28	Mostly Practiced
8. The teacher considers the participation of the learners and the community in developing a indigenized curriculum that incorporates cultural history.	4.53	Highly Practiced
9. The teacher teachers integrates Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSPs) during discussions making sure that the concepts of the IKSPs being used are appropriate and respects cultural values.	4.46	Mostly Practice
10. The teacher explaining the relevance of the IKSPs to the students to further boost their interest to the subject and to indigenous knowledge.	4.39	Mostly Practiced
11. The teacher is resourceful and responsible and make use of several interventions like interviewing Indigenous People (IP) that they know who can share ideas on IKSPs or government units that are applicable.	4.58	Highly Practiced
12. The teacher collect resources or make their own researches on the IKSP that has been observed on the olden days to present from their provinces or community which can be used during classroom discussions.	4.44	Mostly Practiced
13. The teacher seen that education is connected to all aspect of life, the wellbeing of learners.	4.73	Highly Practiced
14. The teacher seen that education is connected to the environment.	4.75	Highly Practiced
15. The teacher believes that the situation of the communities is the starting point for developing the learner's own views, values, priorities, and aspirations.	4.78	Highly Practiced

Grand Mean:

4.59

Highly Practiced

Legend: "Did not Practice at All (1.00 – 1.50)", "Rarely Practice (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Practiced (2.51 – 3.50)", "Mostly Practiced (3.51 – 4.50)", "Highly Practiced (4.51 – 5.00)"

5. Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices of the IPEd schools when grouped into School Profile

5.1 Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Level of Practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and practices of the IPEd Schools when the Respondents are Grouped According to No. of Years of Implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework

Indicators	No. of Years of Implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Practice of IKSPs	1 to 3 years	0.00	0.409	0.522	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	4 to 6 years	0.00				
	7 to 9 years	62.47				
	10 years and above	58.23				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

5.2 Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Level of Practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and practices of the IPEd Schools when Grouped According to No. of IP Students Enrolled

Indicators	No. of IP Students Enrolled	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Practice of IKSPs	1-25	61.65	0.089	0.993	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	26-50	58.98				
	51-75	61.11				
	76-100	61.39				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

5.3 Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Level of Practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and practices of the IPEd Schools when the Respondents are Grouped According to No. of Schools Trained for Indigenous People Education

Indicators	No. of Teachers Trained for Indigenous People Education	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Practice of IKSPs	Not Trained on Indigenous Education Policy Framework	68.57	26.261	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	28.14				
	Trained in the Division Level	57.10				
	Trained in the Regional Level	97.62				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

5.4 Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Level of Practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and practices of the IPed Schools when the Respondents are Grouped According to No. of Schools Trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices

Indicators	No. of Teachers Trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Practice of IKSPs	Not Trained on Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	67.78	25.817	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Trained in the District Level	30.83				
	Trained in the Division Level	54.00				
	Trained in the Regional Level	90.00				
	Trained in the National Level	0.00				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

6. Test for Significant Relationship Between the Level of Implementation of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework and Level of Practice of the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices

Indicators	Level of Practice of IKSPs				
	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Curriculum Design, Competencies, and Content	0.270	Weak Positive Correlation	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
Teaching Methodologies and Strategies	0.429	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Learning Space and Environment	0.294	Weak Positive Correlation	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Learning Resources	0.266	Weak Positive Correlation	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
Teacher Training	0.661	Strong Positive Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Classroom Assessment	0.479	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

7. Challenges Encountered by the School

7.1 Mean Scores on the Challenges Encountered by the School in terms of Implementation of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework

Do you encounter the following challenges in the implementation of the IPED Policy Framework?	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Excluding Indigenous knowledge and traditional language (mother-tongue) instruction in the curriculum	4.12	High Challenge

2. Lack of educational materials with socio-cultural relevance.	4.02	High Challenge
3. Avoiding any institutionalized partnership with the indigenous community (lack of community engagement).	4.18	High Challenge
4. Standardizing the curriculum without considering the particular setting (no contextualization or indigenization).	4.26	High Challenge
5. No availability assessment tool appropriate to the standards, competencies, skills, and concepts being covered.	4.18	High Challenge
6. Maintaining a disconnect between indigenous knowledge and skills and national standard curricula.	4.11	High Challenge
7. Excluding indigenous elders and their traditional knowledge from the educational process.	4.09	High Challenge
8. Ignoring both indigenous and non-indigenous concepts within a historical and political context.	4.11	High Challenge
Grand Mean:	4.13	High Challenge

7.2 Mean Scores on the Challenges Encountered by the School in terms of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices

Do you encounter the following challenges in the following situation?	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Learner's Disinterest in Indigenous Knowledge.	4.37	High Challenge
2. Exclusion/Non-application of the IKSP in the subject matter.	4.21	High Challenge
3. Lack of IKSPs materials (e.g., traditional musical instruments, etc).	3.98	High Challenge
4. Absence of Training/Seminars about IKSPs."	3.80	High Challenge
5. Absence of culturally appropriate learning resources and environment like books, etc.	4.14	High Challenge
6. Lack of written knowledge or facts about IKSPs and insufficient evidence, visual aids, and other resources during discussions.	4.07	High Challenge
7. Non-participation of the IP Community in school programs and projects.	4.21	High Challenge
8. Discrimination among IP learners.	2.82	Moderate Challenge
9. Exclusion and disregard of indigenous knowledge in planning and implementing education programs, policies, and curricula..	3.96	High Challenge
10. Inequitable access and provision of basic education to Indigenous Peoples.	4.02	High Challenge
Grand Mean:	3.81	High Challenge

8. Strategies Applied by the School to Address the Challenges Encountered

8.1 Mean Scores on the Strategies Applied by the School to Address the Challenges Encountered in terms of Implementation of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework

Strategies Applied to Address the Challenges in the Implementation of the IPED Policy Framework	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Integrating Indigenous knowledge and traditional language (mother-tongue) instruction in the curriculum	4.15	More Applied
2. Localizing and indigenizing of educational materials with socio-cultural relevance.	4.32	More Applied
3. Establishing institutionalized partnership between the indigenous community. .(community engagement).	4.34	More Applied
4. Contextualization and indigenization of the curriculum to a particular setting.	4.40	More Applied
5. Localizing assessment tool appropriate to the standards, competencies, skills and concepts being covered.	4.69	Most Applied
6. Establishing links between indigenous knowledge and skills and national standard curricula.	4.61	Most Applied
7. Involving the indigenous elders as holders of traditional knowledge and speakers of the indigenous language.	4.70	Most Applied
8. Accommodating indigenous and non-indigenous concepts that are evolving in a historical and political context.	4.68	Most Applied
Grand Mean:	4.49	More Applied

8.2 Mean Scores on the Actions Taken by the School to Address the Challenges Encountered in terms of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices

Strategies Applied to Address the Challenges of the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Providing interest-enhancing intervention to get learner's interest on the Indigenous Knowledge	4.45	Most Applied
2. Integration/application of the IKSP in the subject matter.	4.69	Most Applied
3. Utilizing available IKSPs materials (example: traditional musical instrument, etc.)	4.70	More Applied
4. Including training/seminars about IKSPs on Teachers Development Program	4.30	More Applied
5. Providing culturally appropriate learning resources and environment like books, etc.	4.61	Most Applied
6. Researching, gathering and compiling of written knowledge or facts about IKSPs and sufficient evidences, visual aids and other resources during discussions.	4.49	More Applied
7. Seeking the participation of the IP Community in school programs and projects	4.70	Most Applied
8. Implementing a No Discrimination Policy/ Child Friendly School Policy in School.	4.62	Most Applied
9. Recognizing and including the indigenous knowledge in planning and implementing education programs, policies and curricula in the school.	4.45	More Applied
10. Provisions of universal and equitable access of all IPs to quality and relevant Basic Education	4.55	More Applied
Grand Mean:	4.56	Most Applied

DISCUSSION

1. School profile of the IP schools in the CALABARZON Region
 - 1.1 The school profile of the IP schools in the CALABARZON Region as to No. of years in implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework is within the 7 to 9 years category, many institutions or organizations have been implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework for a similar duration
 - 1.2 The school profile of the IP schools in the CALABARZON in terms of IP students enrolled, majority of respondents (52%) reported having 1-25 Indigenous People students enrolled in their institutions. A significant portion of the sample comprises institutions with relatively smaller numbers of IP students.
 - 1.3 The school profile of the IP schools in the CALABARZON Region as to number of schools trained/not trained for indigenous people education. A significant proportion of schools has not received training in either Indigenous Education Policy Framework or Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices, highlighting the need for more comprehensive training initiatives.
 - 1.4 The school profile of the IP schools in the CALABARZON Region as to No. of teachers trained for Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices. Nearly half of the schools, 47% of the total, have received training at the division level. This level seems to have been more effective in promoting IKSPs training among schools.
2. The level of implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework among elementary schools
 - 2.1 The level of implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework among elementary schools as to Curriculum Design, Competencies and Content got a mean of 4.58 with an interpretation of fully implemented.
 - 2.2 The level of implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework among elementary schools as to Teaching Methodologies and strategies got a mean of 4.43 with an interpretation of mostly implemented.
 - 2.3 The level of implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework among elementary schools as to Learning Space and Environment got a mean of 4.44 with an interpretation of mostly implemented.
 - 2.4 The level of implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework among elementary schools as to Learning Resources got a mean of 4.20 with an interpretation of mostly implemented.
 - 2.5 The level of implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework among elementary schools as to Teachers Training got a mean of 4.32 with an interpretation of moderately implemented.
 - 2.6 The level of implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework among elementary schools as to Classroom Assessment got a mean of 4.42 with an interpretation of mostly implemented.

3. The significant difference in the level of implementation of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework when grouped into school profile

- 3.1 In terms of the No. of Years of Implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of the National People Education Policy Framework when grouped into demography is rejected as to curriculum design, competencies, and content. Likewise, the null hypothesis is rejected in terms of learning space and environment as it gained a p-value of 0.049 which is lower than 0.05 level of significance. Furthermore, the null hypothesis is rejected in terms of learning resources as it gained a p-value of 0.029 which is lower than 0.05 level of significance. Moreover, the null hypothesis is rejected in terms of classroom assessment with the p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. On the other hand, the null hypothesis is accepted in terms of teaching methodologies and strategies and teachers' training with the p-values of 0.045 and 0.073.
- 3.2 In terms of IP students enrolled, Curriculum Design, Competencies, and Content, Teaching Methodologies and Strategies, Learning Resources, and Teacher Training, gained the p-values of 0.128, 0.273, 0.123, 0.126, respectively. This means that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of the National IP Education Policy Framework as to the number of IP enrollees. On the other hand, the null hypothesis is rejected in terms of classroom assessment with the p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. This means that significant difference in the level of implementation of the National IP Education Policy Framework as to the number of IP enrollees and the classroom assessment is affected. The less the learners, the easy the classroom assessment, and vice versa.
- 3.3 In terms of the No. of school trained for Indigenous people education, curriculum design, competencies, and content and teaching methodologies and strategies, the p-values are 0.000 and 0.040 which is less than 0.05 level of significance, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Similarly, learning resources, teachers' training, and classroom assessment received the p-values less than 0.05 level of significance indication that the null hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, in terms of learning space and environment the p-value is 0.330 which is greater than 0.05 which lead to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of the National People Education Policy Framework when grouped into demography as to learning space and environment.
- 3.4 In terms of the No. of schools Trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices, the curriculum Design, Competencies, and Content, Teaching Methodologies and Strategies, Learning Space and Environment, Learning Resources, and Classroom Assessment, the gained p-values are 0.000, 0.022, 0.013, 0.000, 0.001, respectively. Since the gained p-values are less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of the National People Education Policy Framework when grouped into demography is rejected. On the other hand, the teachers' training received a p-value of 0.064 which is greater than 0.05 level

of significance, the null hypothesis is statistically accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of the National People Education Policy Framework when grouped into demography as to teachers' training.

4. Level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices among of the IPEd schools in CALABARZON Region got a mean of 4.59 with an interpretation of fully implemented.
5. The significant difference in the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices of the IPEd schools when grouped into school profile
 - 5.1 In terms of the No. of Years of Implementing the Indigenous Education Policy Framework got a p value of 0.522 is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices of the IPEd schools when grouped into School Profile is statistically accepted. This mean that the level of practice is not affected by the length of years of implementation of IPEd Policy Framework, and vice versa.
 - 5.2 In terms of the No. of IP Students Enrolled got a p-value of 0.993 is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices of the IPEd schools when grouped into School Profile is statistically accepted. This means that the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices among the IP schools is not affected by the total number of IP learners.
 - 5.3 In terms of the No. of Schools Trained for Indigenous People Education got a -value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices of the IPEd schools when grouped into School Profile is statistically rejected. This means that the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices among the IP schools is affected by the training received by the IP teachers. The more the training the IP teacher attended the high the level of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices, and vice versa.
 - 5.4 In terms of the No. of Schools Trained for the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices of the IPEd schools when grouped into School Profile is statistically rejected. This means that there is significant difference in the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices and the number of teachers trained in IKSPs. This means that the higher the number of trained teachers in different levels, the higher the possibility to preserve the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices, and vice versa.
6. The significant relationship between the level of implementation of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework and level of practice of the Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices has less than 0.05 level of significance for Curriculum Design, Competencies, and Content, Teaching, Methodologies and Strategies, Learning Space and Environment, Learning Resources, Teachers'

Training, and Classroom Assessment. , the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the level of implementation of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework and level of practice of the Indigenous Knowledge is rejected. This means that there is significant relationship among the variables of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework and level of practice of the Indigenous Knowledge. Strong positive relationship has been detected in the teachers' training (0.661) and classroom assessment (0.479). On the other hand, weak positive relationship had been detected in the Curriculum Design, Competencies, and Content, Teaching, Methodologies and Strategies, Learning Space and Environment, and Learning Resources.

7. The challenges encountered by the school
 - 7.1 The Challenges Encountered by the School in terms of Implementation of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework got a mean of 4.13 with a verbal interpretation of high challenge.
 - 7.2 The Challenges Encountered by the School in terms of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices got a mean 3.81 with a verbal interpretation of high challenge.
8. The actions taken by the school to address the challenges encountered
 - 8.1 Actions Taken by the School to Address the Challenges Encountered in terms of Implementation of National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy Framework got a mean of 4.49 with a verbal interpretation of significant action taken.
 - 8.2 Actions Taken by the School to Address the Challenges Encountered in terms of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices got a mean of 4.56 with a verbal interpretation of comprehensive action taken.
9. The curriculum model for Indigenous People Education could be developed based on the findings of the study was MJCF IPEd Curriculum Model.

Conclusions

1. The study on Indigenous Peoples (IP) schools in the region highlights a significant trend, with many operating for 7 to 9 years. However, a challenge is the small enrolment of Indigenous students, and a notable portion lacks comprehensive training in the Indigenous Education Policy Framework and Indigenous Knowledge System. About half of the schools have received division-level training. The findings emphasize the need for targeted interventions to address training and enrolment gaps, ensuring the holistic development and cultural relevance of these schools. In elementary schools, the National IP Education Policy is mostly implemented, with some components fully implemented.

2. The study reveals that most components of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework in elementary schools are at least "mostly implemented," with some being "fully implemented." To sustain and enhance effectiveness, it is recommended to establish a consistent regimen of monitoring and evaluation. Schools and educational authorities should implement mechanisms for continuous assessment,

enabling a proactive approach to identify and address areas that may need improvement or adjustment. This ongoing evaluation process is crucial for the continued success of the IP Education Policy framework in elementary education.

3. The study reveals significant variations in implementing the National Indigenous People Education Policy Framework across different school profiles. The duration of implementation is crucial, influencing aspects from curriculum design to classroom assessment. Enrollment of Indigenous students affects classroom assessment, particularly in smaller classes. School training for Indigenous education impacts various facets, while training for Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices notably influences curriculum, competencies, content, learning space, resources, and assessment. No significant differences are found in teachers' training. These findings stress the multifaceted challenges and highlight the need for tailored interventions to address specific needs across diverse school profiles for a more inclusive and effective implementation of Indigenous education policies.

4. The study's findings indicate that the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices among IP schools in CALABARZON is characterized as "fully implemented."

5. The study identifies differences in Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices across school profiles. Duration of implementing the Indigenous Education Policy and enrollment of Indigenous students show no clear impact. Key factors are the number of schools trained for Indigenous education and specifically for Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices. Tailored support and resource allocation based on school profiles are recommended. Recognizing successful schools and encouraging them to share practices is crucial. Schools struggling with implementation should receive additional assistance, including targeted training and capacity-building programs, for comprehensive integration within their educational practices.

6. The study reveals a strong correlation between the implementation of the National Indigenous People Education Policy Framework and the practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices, particularly in teachers' training and classroom assessment. This underscores the importance of comprehensive strategies that simultaneously address policy execution and on-the-ground practices, ensuring a harmonized and culturally responsive educational environment.

7. The study shows schools encounter significant challenges in implementing the National Indigenous People Education Policy Framework and Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices, consistently rated as high. This emphasizes the urgent need for focused attention and strategic interventions to address these challenges and ensure effective integration within the educational system. Recognizing these obstacles calls for a conclusive and comprehensive approach to support schools in successfully implementing Indigenous education initiatives.

8. Schools have proactively taken substantial measures to address challenges in implementing the National Indigenous People Education Policy Framework and

Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices. This showcases a commendable commitment to overcoming obstacles and successfully integrating these policies and practices within the educational framework. These efforts reflect a conclusive dedication to fostering a more inclusive and culturally responsive educational environment for Indigenous communities.

Recommendations

1. Nearly half of the schools have received training at the division level. Thus, it is recommended that implement continuous professional development programs to keep teachers and staff updated on best practices, curriculum updates, and changes in policies related to indigenous education.
2. The study finds that most components of the National Indigenous People (IP) Education Policy framework in elementary schools are at least "mostly implemented," with some "fully implemented." It is recommended to consistently monitor and evaluate the implementation level. Schools and educational authorities should establish mechanisms for ongoing assessment to identify areas needing improvement or adjustment.
3. The number of IP students enrolled affects classroom assessment, indicating that smaller classes make assessment easier. The number of schools trained for Indigenous People education affects curriculum design, competencies, content, teaching methodologies, learning resources, teachers' training, and classroom assessment. The number of schools trained for Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices significantly impacts curriculum design, competencies, content, learning space, learning resources, and classroom assessment. However, teachers' training does not show significant differences. Thus, it is recommended to review policies regularly to make sure they still work for different types of schools.
4. It is recommended to involve ongoing collaboration with indigenous communities, elders, and knowledge holders to ensure the preservation and transmission of traditional wisdom and practices to younger generations.
5. The study revealed that there is a significant difference in the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices when grouped by school profile. Thus, it is recommended to provide tailored support and resources to schools based on their specific profiles. Schools that have successfully implemented IKSP should be acknowledged and encouraged to share their best practices with others. Schools that are struggling to fully implement IKSP may require additional assistance, including training and capacity-building programs.
6. The study found a significant relationship between the level of implementation of the National Indigenous People Education Policy Framework and the level of practice of Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices. Thus, it is recommended that policy makers and educational authorities should prioritize the effective execution of this

framework, ensuring that its principles and guidelines are embedded in the educational system.

7. The study revealed that challenges encountered by schools in implementing the National Indigenous People Education Policy Framework and Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices are rated as high challenges. Hence, it is strongly recommended to undertake a comprehensive needs assessment aimed at pinpointing the specific challenges encountered by schools in implementing the National Indigenous People Education Policy Framework (NIPEPF) and Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices (IKSP). This assessment should actively involve input from teachers, school administrators, indigenous communities, and various stakeholders, ensuring a thorough and holistic understanding of the challenges at hand.

8. The study uncovered that schools have proactively implemented substantial measures to tackle challenges in implementing the National Indigenous People Education Policy Framework and Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices. In light of this, a crucial recommendation is to formulate sustainability plans to uphold the long-term continuity of these comprehensive actions. These plans should delineate strategies for institutionalizing successful interventions and practices, ensuring a sustained and impactful integration within the educational system.

9. The study suggests that a innovative curriculum model for Indigenous People Education could be developed based on the findings, with the proposed MJCF IPed Curriculum Model. Thus, it is recommended to disseminate the MJCF IPed Curriculum Model and related resources widely within indigenous communities, educational institutions, and relevant organizations. Facilitate knowledge sharing through workshops, seminars, and conferences.

10. Future researchers should take a closer look at specific Indigenous People (IP) schools in the region. This way, they can understand the challenges these schools face and the strategies they use when implementing the National Indigenous People Education Policy Framework and Indigenous Knowledge System and Practices. By focusing on specific schools, researchers can get more detailed information and better understand what works well in these communities. This could help create better strategies and recommendations for improving education in Indigenous communities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to the commencement of this research, informed consent was obtained from all participants involved in the study. Participants were provided with detailed information about the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits of the research. They were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without facing any consequences. This research project received approval from the Deped CLABARZON Regional Office before data collection commenced. All collected data were treated with the utmost confidentiality. Personal information was anonymized, and any identifying

details were removed to protect the privacy of participants. Only the researcher had access to the raw data. The research was conducted with transparency and honesty. Any conflicts of interest, funding sources, or affiliations that may have influenced the research were disclosed. The reporting of findings accurately reflects the data collected, and any limitations are acknowledged.

Acknowledgments

The researcher extends her heartfelt gratitude to Almighty God for giving her plenty of blessings such as the gift of wisdom, knowledge, and health, for her strong will and determination to endure the hardships and pain, and to keep on holding in accomplishing this manuscript. The researcher also expresses her appreciation to the following who extended their most valued assistance for the realization of this undertaking. Marinduque State College, for bridging the needs of teachers and school administrators for continuing professional development; MSC-QECI Extension Program, for the non-stop leveling up of better education in the Province of Quezon; Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr., Chair, Extended Graduate Programs, a God-fearing, brilliant, and perfectionist professor, for his untiring support words of encouragement, technical assistance, and continuous guidance to the researcher in order for this study to be a success; Dr. Rizalie M. Lim, Dean of Graduate Studies, QECI, for her encouragement and support; Dr. Rex Emmanuel L. Asuncion, her very supportive research adviser, for sharing his knowledge and expertise in supervising the researcher in writing the manuscript; Dr. Annalyn J. Decena, for lending a helping hand especially in editing the manuscript and for her expertise in supervising the researcher in writing the manuscript. and The committee on oral examination with the chairman Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, Dr. Liza Marie L. Manoos, Dr. Romulo H. Malvar, Dr. Julietta Q. Nabos, and Dr. Rogel L. Limpiada for their comments and suggestion that contributed a lot to the improvement of the manuscript, Dr. Joy S. Montejo and Dr. Julieta L. Go, her editor and copy editor, for sharing their expertise in checking and editing the manuscript. Ma'am Liezl Manoy, for her unwavering assistance.

To the Regional Director, Schools Division Superintendents, District Supervisors, School Heads and Teachers of DepEd CALABARZON, for permitting the researcher to conduct research in the region. To Dr. Gilbert C. Alva, her district supervisor for the moral support. Patrick and Sofia, her children, for giving her strength, inspiration and joy for keeping her up in time of difficulties. Her brother and sisters, for their moral and financial support.

The researcher will never forget the unconditional support given by her family and all the people who gave her guidance and strength to finally achieved her dreams to write a paper that gave her privilege to a Doctoral Degree Graduate.

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